

Table 1. Recovery of ¹⁵N-urea and yield of Lemont rice.^a Louisiana, USA.

Treatment no.	Treatment (% applied urea)				¹⁵ N recovery (%)				Grain yield (g/pot)
	Transplanting	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Milk stage	Soil	Roots	Shoots	Grain	
1	100	—	—	—	21	5	10	22	26.2
2	50	30	10	10	14	5	15	28	26.7
3	50	10	30	10	24	8	14	29	28.7
4	25	25	25	25	16	7	14	29	27.2
C	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	16.1
LSD (0.05)					ns	2	ns	ns	3.1

^a Mean of 4 observations. C = control, no N applied.

Table 2. N derived from fertilizer in rice plant components. Louisiana, USA.

Treatment no.	N derived from fertilizer ^a (%)		
	Roots	Shoots	Panicles
1	22	32	33
2	22	37	37
3	30	34	35
4	27	38	39

^a Mean of 4 observations.

long and 15 cm internal diameter). Deionized H₂O containing 0.15 g P/kg soil and 0.20 g K/kg soil was added to establish water depth of 2-4 cm.

Three 20-d-old Lemont seedlings previously grown in a sand culture were transplanted into each of 20 pots. Four N treatments were applied using urea-¹⁵N (29.991 atom %) at 0.44 g urea N/pot. Urea-¹⁵N solutions were injected into the rice root zone. Each N treatment, including control, was replicated four times.

At harvest, each pot was destructively sampled and total Kjeldahl N and ¹⁵N content determined on soil and plant components (roots, shoots, grain).

Plant recovery of applied urea-¹⁵N was from 58% in the roots, 10-15% in

the shoots, and 22-29% in the grain (Table 1). Total plant ¹⁵N recovery was 38-51%; highest recovery was with treatment 3. Control grain yields were significantly different from those of the N treatments.

About 60% of the ¹⁵N taken up by the rice plant was in the grain. ¹⁵N remaining in the soil after harvest ranged from 14 to 24%. About 34% of the ¹⁵N applied was unaccounted for.

The two sources of N to rice are soil N (% NdfS) and fertilizer N (% NdfF). In treatment 1, plant N was 69% NdfS and 31% NdfF; in treatment 2, 65% NdfS and 35% NdfF; in treatment 3, 67% NdfS and 33% NdfF; and in treatment 4, 64% NdfS and 36% NdfF. Rice uptake of fertilizer N was significantly correlated with grain yield ($r=0.634^{**}$).

Percentage of NdfF in the root, shoot, and panicle rice tissues is shown in Table 2. Panicle NdfF accounted for 33-39% of the total panicle N content, slightly higher than the 32-38% NdfF taken up by the rice shoots. NdfF was lowest in the root tissues. □

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Comparison of prilled urea (PU) and large granule urea (LGU) and time of application on rice yield

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We compared PU (26-30 mg) and LGU (6-8 mm diameter) at 30, 60, and 90 kg N/ha broadcast in saturated soil at 4 rice growth stages in a 1986 dry season field experiment. The 10 treatments (including no N) were in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Soil was sandy loam (Aeric Haplaquept) with pH 5.2, 0.47% organic C, CEC 5.7 meq/100 g, 290 kg available N/ha (alkaline permanganate method),

15.7 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 110 kg K/ha (ammonium acetate extract).

Seedlings of Lalat (130 d duration) were transplanted on 18 Jan. All plots received 13.2 kg P, 24.9 kg K/ha at transplanting (TP).

Effect of PU and LGU on yield and N efficiency. Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, 1986 dry season.

N level (kg/ha)	Time of N application (kg/ha)				Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)		Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)	Yield response (kg grain/kg N)
	TP	7 DT	15 DT	PI	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw			
0	—	1	—	—	2.2	2.6	20.0	11.7	31.7	—	—
30 (PU)	20	2	—	10	2.7	3.0	25.3	17.2	42.5	36.0	16.7
60 (PU)	15	2	30	15	3.1	3.5	31.8	20.9	52.7	35.0	15.0
90 (PU)	22.5	2	45	22.5	3.5	3.6	34.1	22.9	57.0	28.1	14.4
30 (LGU)	20	2	—	10	3.0	3.4	26.9	21.1	48.0	54.3	26.7
30 (LGU)	—	2	—	10	3.0	3.3	28.9	18.3	47.2	51.7	26.7
60 (LGU)	15	2	30	15	3.3	3.5	29.0	17.9	46.9	25.3	18.3
60 (LGU)	—	2	—	20	3.7	3.4	37.7	24.3	62.0	50.5	25.0
90 (LGU)	22.5	12	45	22.5	3.9	4.1	37.5	23.8	61.3	32.9	18.9
90 (LGU)	—	—	—	30	4.4	4.7	42.3	28.7	71.0	43.7	24.4
LSD (0.05)					0.2	0.3	3.3	2.5			

Grain and straw yields and N uptake were significantly higher with 90 kg N/ha from LGU applied 2/3 at 7 d after transplanting (DT) and 1/3 at panicle initiation (PI). Apparent N recovery and yield response (kg grain/kg N) were highest at 30 kg N/ha from LGU applied 2/3 at TP, 1/3 at PI (see table). □